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Qualitative Study on Curriculum and Technological Trends in Smart Education at Secondary School Level-of-Education in Nigeria: A systematic Review

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Abstract

The paper systematically reviewed curriculum and technological trends in smart education at secondary school level-of-education in Nigeria. It therefore discussed the concept of smart education. In view of the growing recognition and adoption of smart education globally, Artificial intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoT) block chain and cloud computing technologies have been deliberated among other several curriculum and technological trends associated with smart education at secondary school level-of-education. It highlighted smart education framework for possible practice and some considerations for effective integration of smart education at secondary school level. Also, the paper concluded that there are several surmountable challenges that may affect the effective integration of smart education at secondary schools in Nigeria including inadequate smart education infrastructures at secondary schools level-of-education and finally among others, it was suggested that opportunities for secondary school teachers and students to attend training aimed at providing relevant ICT skills and knowledge to enable them function effectively should be provided.

Keyword: Smart education, curriculum trends, Smart technology

Introduction

Information Technologies will continue to pervasively transform educational practices around the world. Information Technology (IT) has received considerable attention in education and recognized as one of the most important modern innovation that transformed the teaching and learning process (Haliru & Aliyu, 2023). Various nations are at various pace in technology integration into education system with advanced nations having attained remarkable progress and therefore able to keep

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pace with technological advancement. Efforts to educate citizens and prepare them for the 21st century gave birth to Smart Education (SM) project globally. While some countries (Malaysia, Singapore, Finland, UAE etc.) have already developed and implemented smart education, others are at fluid stage of the project. Smart education aimed to develop individuals into future global citizens by utilizing information technologies to provide 21st century qualities, competencies and responsibilities. Smart education embraces technologies to provide self-learning mode where each students can learn at their speed. It is new paradigm aims at creating smart learners through smart schools. Salem, Mikhalkina and Nikitaeva (2019) see smart education as interdisciplinary area, encompassing many aspects of the educational technologies that cover instruction, training, teaching, learning, pedagogy, communication and collaboration.

Smart Education is a new educational perspective on teaching and learning that redefines the new role of teachers and learners in the learning process and thus seeks to supplant traditional practices which failed to optimize learning for each individual learner. Smart learning environment as technology element of smart education is catalyst for adoption of smart pedagogies. In the view of Zhu and He in Zhu, Sun and Riezebos (2016) the essence of smarter education is to create intelligent environments by using smart technologies, so that smart pedagogies can be facilitated as to provide personalized learning services and empower learners to develop talents of wisdom that have better value orientation, higher thinking quality, and stronger conduct ability.

Implementing technology-facilitated form of education such as SE requires understanding and consideration of basic features, purposes and principles of smart technologies. Smart education take place in smart schools which by their organizational and infrastructural settings take account of individuality and personalized learning. Implementing smart education has to go along way with digitalization of educational landscape.

Concept of Smart Education

The term "smart" according Salem, Mikhalkina and Nikitaeva (2019) is often associated with the technological aspect and the emergence of smart technologies in education, including smart board, smart screens, smart course and a wide range of tools combined in the concept of "smart technologies. Smart education is a new

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educational paradigm that is based on all relevant perspectives, embraces the future as well as the past, and provides clear guidelines for intelligent education in a smarter world (Zhu, Sun & Riezebos, 2016). With increasing role of technologies in education, smart technologies provide many opportunities for accessing content, communication and collaboration in a smart environment. Smart education is the process of optimally managing human, economic and technological resources from educational institutions and research centres (Nwankwo & Mkpa, 2023). Smart education is therefore technology- enhanced, resource-enriched and self-directed form of learning. Smart education involves a comprehensive modernization of all educational processes, as well as methods and technologies used into this process (Salem, Mikhalkina & Nikitaeva, 2019). Smart education can be seen as the education that makes use of smart technologies to shift the educational paradigm in the future. Modernization of educational processes requires proactive engagement with smart learning technologies.

Technology refers to practical application of knowledge for the benefit of people. In the context of education, relevant technologies include such physical things as personal computers and handheld devices as well as non-physical things such as algorithms used to mine data from large data-sets and use findings to make adjustments in terms of information representation and delivery as well as in terms of assessment and evaluation (Spector, 2016). Both teachers and students stand to benefit from smart learning technology. Teachers can use smartphones, tablets and laptops to generate their lessons. Accessibility and affordability have been facilitated by smart technology. Technology plays an important role in availability and accessibility of learning contents including for disabled students (Palanivel, 2020). One of the important characteristic of smart learning technology is “support for learning. To this end, Spector (2016) asserted that Smart learning technologies do need to exhibit support for learning, either directly or through support for instructional design processes intended to promote learning. Idea of learning that is engaging, effective, and efficient should be the focus. Moreover, technologies that empower learners, instructors, or instructional designers by adapting to their needs and situations can be considered smart learning technologies. From foregoing, a technology must possess the features of adaptability and intelligence for to be considered smart learning technology. Adaptability means that the technology has the ability to detect relevant details of the situation and then select, modify and deploy an appropriate response.

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Curriculum and Technological Trends in Smart Education at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Smart technologies are the driving forces of smart education ideology. Advancement in technology has powerful and promising impact on education and mode of instruction. Technology has redefined the roles of major actors in education industry including teachers and students. Today's generation of learners are digital natives and thus require integration of technology into their daily lives both in school and beyond. In this regard, Palanivel (2020) stated that intelligent technologies, such as cloud computing, learning analytics, Big Data, IoT, wearable technology etc., promote the emergence of smart education. Some of the emerging technologies germane to smart education are discussed below:

Artificial Intelligence (AI) at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

AI has remarkably change the educational landscape globally. AI enables the creation of computerized machinery to mimic human behavior and certain psychological features. With AI in education many barriers associated with traditional education are beginning to give way for a more robust, student-centric mode of delivery of education. AI technology can scale easily, quickly and facilitate a one-on-one interface with a learner (Palanivel, 2020).

Block chain Technology at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Security and quality of information and all important transaction is key in any industry. Block chain enables protection of digital transaction in a smart education. Block chain help to minimize threat to security of records, prevent alteration and unauthorized access. The most common use of this technology is for providing authentic records of students' credentials and competences.

Big Data Technology at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Big data has transformed education from traditional to smart system. Like other smart learning technologies, big data platform can offer both a data archival and advanced analytics to the challenges in education. Big data analytics can be applied to all of the areas of student enrollment, student management, and reporting with advanced research. The advantages of using Big Data in education are reliability, flexibility and efficiency (Palanivel, 2020).

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Cloud Computing Technology at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

As smart technology, cloud computing enables storage, management and processing of data using network of internet-hosted computers instead of local sever or personal computer. Palanivel (2020) identifies the following role of cloud computing in smart education: Creating a flexible, unified and open platform for education information; sharing of educational resources among developers, teachers and students; and alleviating the information gap between different areas of today's education.

Some of the advantages of cloud computing system include reduced cost, wide access to educational contents, enhanced teaching and learning, openness to new technologies, offline usage among others.

Data Science Technology at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

The data science model understand the problem domain and the data, preparation of the data, mining of the data and evaluation of the discovered knowledge. For analysis, it give rise to new important methodological developments in smart education. The development requires experts from educational science and data science.

Machine Learning Technology at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Machine Learning (ML) technology is a subset of AI. ML applications designed to benefit the education community, such as learning analytics, content analytics, scheduling algorithms, grading systems, cognitive psychology and active learning and experimental design. ML has the potential to improve student engagement, create clearer communication channels between teachers and students, and develop less biased grading systems.

Internet of Thing (IoT) at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

IoT is described as an ecosystem of connected things coupled with sensors, that capture information in their environment, store, process and analyze either at the device itself or in the cloud or remotely to create value. IoT provides opportunity for improving the quality learning and efficiency of administrative tasks in education. Smart campus, smart classroom, digital content, smart examination, remote learning, campus safety are among other results of IoT (Planivel, 2020). Similarly IoT

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has given rise to a number of applications an IoT-powered appliances for smart education. For instance smart lightning and smart heating can be ensure efficient energy consumption and control of the cooling systems of smart classrooms.

Learning Analytics Technology at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

This aspect of smart technology plays crucial role in smart education. Learning analytics is defined as the use of educational data and educational models to predict the progress and performance of students, and the ability to take action on that information (Palanivel, 2020). This technology improves and optimizes the learning capabilities. This analytics technology can be used to find the educational sentiments of students and what subjects they should learn to reach their desired level of competence.

Smart Education Framework for Practice at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Smart education practice requires smart learning environment that promote efficient and effective learning. Smart Education redefines the role of teachers and learners in education. As such new skills and capabilities are key to this new educational perspective. The adoption of new pedagogies to transform practice at scale requires connections between pedagogy and technology, underpinned by knowledge of how to bring about change (Shoikova, Nikolov & Kovatcheva, 2017). The three essential elements that underpinned smart education framework proposed by in Zhu, Sun and Riezebos (2016) are as follows: Teaching Presence, Technology and Learner presence, respectively.

Teaching Presence at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

This describes the teaching role in a smart education system as instructional design, facilitation and direct instruction, and technological support. Teaching presence refers to student-centred, personalized, and collaborative pedagogical models to design learning in technology-facilitated environments, facilitating the learning process by promoting interactions and providing feedback/direct instructions, and supporting learners to use technologies (Zhu, Sun & Riezebos, 2016).

The three major components of teaching presence are *instructional design, facilitation and direct instruction, and technological support.*

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Instructional design. This involves setting up learning objectives, organizing learning activities, and providing rules and guidance in a technology-facilitated environment. Technology use in education has led to emergence of new instructional approaches characterized as student-centric, personalized and collaborative. Students' active participation is central to student-centred approach to teaching. With smart technologies, Smart education helped to overcome barriers in traditional practice such as meeting the individual differences by way of personalized learning paths (Web-based learning system). Collaboration is on the notion of the knowledge building community where the focus is on problem solving and collective knowledge building rather than passing on knowledge.

Facilitation and direct instruction: unlike in traditional setting, in the smart education environment the teacher assume the new responsibilities of facilitator and encourage participation among the students. The teacher also provides intellectual and scholarly leadership and share their subject matter knowledge with students" (Anderson et al., 2001).

Technological support. Teachers are required to provide technical support to the students. For teachers to function effectively they have to competent enough to support the learners to achieve the goal of smart education. Digital divides among students from high-tech and low-tech homes further make this imperative.

Learner presence at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Succinctly put, learner presence refers to proactive role a learner plays in the learning process. Zhu, Sun and Riezebos (2016) conceptualize learner presence in the smart education framework as consisting of three major components: *autonomous learner, collaborative learner and an efficient technology user.*

Autonomous learner. Individuality is key to smart education and learners require a match between their personal talents and interests and learning experiences provided for optimal learning. Proactive participation is promoted by personal abilities, desires and interests.

Collaborative learner. Although individuality is dominant factor in technology-facilitated learning setting, collaboration plays important role as it help students to

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learn from each other. Collaborative learners acquire skills such teamwork and role identification among others.

Efficient technology user. For optimal learning to occur in the smart education environment, learners should be able use technology for specific learning purpose. Digital skills play fundamental role for learners to efficiently interact with smart technologies.

Facilitating the integration of Smart Education at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Smart education is an embryonic project in Nigeria with smart schools being set up in every state in the country. The universal Basic Education Commission had recently signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with Korean international Commission Agency to kick-start the project in Nigeria. As new education practice, implementation of smart education is not without flaws. Some of the considerations for effective integration of smart education in the country are discussed below:

Development of highly trained teachers at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Smart education redefines the role of teachers. The interaction between internet of things (IoT) and learners is facilitated by competent teachers with relevant technological and pedagogical knowledge and skills. Education system in Nigeria has been plagued by inadequate trained teachers which affect the implementation of any programme. To this end, Haliru and Aliyu (2023) stated that teachers grappled with problem of lack of adequate training on how to function effectively using the new technologies. Smart education requires trained teachers that can operate smart technologies such as smart board and smart phones, tablet in order to facilitate learning and interaction in smart learning environment. Both smart educators and learners must develop digital skills for optimum participation in smart education.

Equally important are the related concepts of computer self-efficacy and computer literacy. While the former implies judgment of one's capability to use computer the later refers to one's ability to execute assigned tasks with computer. Both computer self-efficacy and literacy have significant impact on teachers' and students' computer usage in technology-enhanced learning environment.

Provision of sustainable technological infrastructure at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Smart schools are uniquely different from conventional schools in terms of provision of smart technologies. Smart devices- smart board/interactive white board, smart table, mobile technologies (tablet, laptop) and video conferencing are associated infrastructure available in smart classrooms. No one is able to use and enjoy the benefits of electronic devices and information technologies unless connected with internet (Idris & Benjamin, 2022). Poor or lack internet connectivity and irregular power supply are among major setbacks to technology integration in education in Nigeria. There is a plethora of smart technologies to create the environment for learning to happen. Such technologies require reliable connectivity and electricity to function and facilitate learning.

Adequate funding is key to success at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Procurement of ICT infrastructures and their regular maintenance and replacement of malfunctioned ones as well as internet subscriptions justify a need for funds successful functioning of smart schools. Nwankwo and Mpka (2023) stated that government has to make funds available for the equipment and manpower required for the implementation of smart schools.

Formulation of policy framework at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Policies serve important purpose not only in education but all aspects of human endeavor. Government should formulate policies to guide and regulate the implementation of smart education in the country. It is through these policies that personnel development and recruitment can be controlled and regulated.

Conclusion

Smart education hold a promising future for secondary school level of education in Nigeria. It is a form of education that can be best described as technology-enhanced, resource-enriched and self-directed learning. The emergence of smart education was

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facilitated by irresistible advancement of technologies and their wide spread application particularly in educational sector. Smart education has become an integral part of initiatives to improve the quality of secondary education in Nigeria. This educational practice has long been operational in some developed countries, it appears to be new and relatively recent innovation in developing countries. There are several surmountable challenges that may affect the implementation of smart education in secondary schools in Nigeria and other developing countries. One fundamental issue is that of inadequate smart education infrastructures in secondary schools which government must give priority in order to achieve the desired results.

Suggestions

1. There should be opportunities for secondary school teachers and students to attend training aimed at providing relevant ICT skills and knowledge to enable them function effectively in smart schools;
2. There should be synergy between government and private organization in order to make funds available for provision of needed equipment, facilities and services, internet connectivity and electricity inclusive; and
3. Functional policy framework to regulate and facilitate this new perspective of education is needed.

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